

Evaluation of Degree and the Effect of Order in the Family on Violence against Children A Survey among Guidance School Students in Gilanegharb City in Iran

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Abstract—A review of the literature found that Domestic violence and child maltreatment co-occur in many families, the purpose of this study attempts to emphasize the factors relating to intra-family relationships (order point of view) on violence against the children, For this purpose a survey technique on the sample size amounted 200 students of governmental guidance schools of city of Gilanegharb in country of Iran were considered. For measurement of violence against the children (VAC) the CTS scaled has been used. The results showed that children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year. degree of order in family is high. Explanation result indicated that the order variables in family including collective thinking, empathy, communal co-circumstance have significant effects on VAC.

Keywords—Violence, domestic violence, violence against children, order, guidance school, family, children.

I. INTRODUCTION

VIOLENCE makes life rough and imposition, also causes psychological and physical injuries which will never be improved. Women and children are more in the center of attack. Children are affected by domestic violence in a variety of ways. Domestic violence in the household is often accompanied by other major developmental risk factors for children such as poverty, female-headed Household and low education level of primary care giver [1]. Children in violent households may be involved in the violence by feeling the need to call for help or by being identified as a cause of the dispute that led to the abuse. Children who live in violent households also are at risk for physical injury both parentally and postnatally [2]. Children often are inadvertent victims of violence between adult family members. Christian et al [2]. reviewed the records of 139 children who presented to the emergency department with injuries resulting from domestic violence and found the age of the child victim to range from 2 weeks to 17 years, with a mean age of 5 years.

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Domestic violence within the family places a child at increased risk for sexual and physical abuse. Kaufman and Henrich estimate that approximately 40% of children who witness domestic violence are also physically abused [3]. The severity of the domestic violence appears predictive of the severity of the child abuse [4]. Children living with domestic violence are at risk not only physically but also psychologically and emotionally [5]. The negative changes in parenting that result from domestic violence are what lead to the child's emotional and behavioral problems, not the domestic violence directly [6].

Adult domestic violence is also associated with child abuse [7]. There is evidence that children who are victims of or witnesses to domestic violence have more emotional and social problems than children not exposed to such violence [8]. It has also been found that developmental impairments and psychological problems may affect these children throughout adolescence and into adulthood [9].

Child exposure to adult domestic violence is associated with significantly greater behavioral, emotional, and cognitive functioning problems among children, as well as adjustment difficulties that continue into young adulthood [10].

A considerable amount of child additionally disposes on physical violence at the home directly, effect of violence indirectly through enforcement of violence of father on Mother, children will be injured mentally and physically. A 1996 survey by the Australian Bureau of Statistics found that 23% of women who have been married or in a de facto relationship have experienced violence a partner [11]

Sixty eight percent of women who had experienced violence in a previous relationship stated that at some time during the relationship they had children in their care [11]. Forty six percent of these women said that these children had witnessed the violence.

Smith [12] found that after more than 3 months separation from the violent parent, 42% of children surveyed displayed behavior problems that warranted clinical intervention.

Straus [13] estimated yet an even higher level of exposure using retrospective accounts by adults of their teen years. He estimated that there may be as many as 10 million American teenagers exposed to adult domestic violence each year. Carlson [14] has more recently raised her estimate as a result of additional studies. She now conservatively estimates that from 10% to 20% of American children are exposed to adult

domestic violence each year [14]. Thompson, Saltzman, and Johnson[15] report that 33.2% of 962 Children and Youth Canadian abused women and 40.2% of US battered women responding in national surveys stated that their children had witnessed domestic violence events.

More recent meta-analyses by Kitzmann, Gaylord, Holt, and Kenny[16] and Wolfe, Crooks, Lee, McIntyre-Smith, and Jaffe [17] have shown children exposed to domestic violence to exhibit significantly worse problems than children not so exposed [9]. It is estimated that between 20 and 30% of women and 7.5% of men have been physically and/or sexually abused by an intimate partner at some point in their lives [18]. Fifty percent of all female homicides are the result of intimate partner violence [19]. Chronic but often non-specific problems are often reported by the adult victim. They include headaches, sleep disorders, GI discomfort and bowel problems, depression, fatigue, anxiety and post traumatic stress disorder [20]. Research examining the effects of domestic violence on young children revealed that, according to mother's reports, half of the children witnessed at least 60% of the violence [12]. These findings indicate a major social problem which has long term negative effects on children. These effects include anxiety, depression, aggressive behavior, decreased self-esteem, disobedience, emotional distress and carrying out abuse in the future [21]. Smith [12] found that after more than 3 months separation from the violent parent, 42% of children surveyed displayed behavior problems that warranted clinical intervention. Children are often directly involved in the violent situation either through witnessing the violence, being abused themselves, or suffering as a result of parental stress and frustration.

This paper tries to cover the violence against children (VAC) also violence against mothers by fathers (VAM).

Framework:

For domestic violence are many definitions. Tailor and Garbarino pay attention to nature of violence, Some of other scholar have mentioned some factors related to violence such as dystrophy, parents disability in satisfying children with enough food, sanitary problems, dirty places for living, preventing children from school, punishing and... [22]. Behaviors often attributed to domestic violence exposure may also derive from the child's concurrent victimization at the hands of his or her parent or caregiver [10]. The wide range of behaviors and consequences associated with exposure to domestic violence found in these reviews indicate that the relationship between exposure and possible impacts is complex [23]. There are many models for explanation of domestic violence e.g Wolf have posed transitional model for intensity of conflict between parents and children, in this model stress is a factor which intensifies the probability conflicts among family. Parents disability on facing the problems in their lives cause VAC. Tonti man and his colleagues have posed cognitive-behavioral model. Mack fal have posed social information processing model [24] Life cycle model by Reder and Duncan ,this model pays attention to the international theories which in turn emphasis on VAC[25].

For defining of domestic violence served models have been used, including theories which have regarded the family inter

relations. To achieve this we have used the Chalabi model which is base on Parsons theory.

Chalabi explains that "interactions and individuals" are two main factors within order formation in families and combination of these two brings order, at micro-level. in the A.G.I.L Parsons framework tells with the formation of "us" we can speak of a kind of micro social order. This social order, instantaneously, involves "individuals", "interactions", and "us". the "us" which is based on "individuals" and "interactions". To preserve "orders" and "interaction patterns", micro social order confront four problems[26]. including: 1- collective thinking (L), 2- company (G) 3- empathy (I), and 4-communal circumstance(A) [26].

II. METHOD

This research is survey and information have been collected by questioner, population is the city of Gilanegharb in Iran , samples are 200 students of guidance school in 2007 , selected by sample of systematic random. reliability and validity of variables have been considered, by scale of Alpha and Factor analysis.

Measurement:

A. Order in Family (Independent Variables)

For measuring order in family used been below variables:

1. Collective thinking 2. Company 3. Empathy 4. communal circumstance. Each independent variables by codes : never=0, very little = 1, little= 2, moderate = 3 , much = 4 , very much = 5 , ever = 6, e.g. questions raised to this way:" To which extent there has been consult within your family?"

Never very little little moderate much
very much ever

operational independent variables are available at Table I.

Questioner of order in family:

1. To which extent there has been consult within your family?
2. To which extent there has been consult on children nurture within you parents?
3. To which extent there has been consult on families meeting within your family?
4. To which extent there has been consult on buying house wares within your family?
5. How much your parent loves each other?
6. How much does your father love you?
7. How much does your mother love you?
8. How much do you love your father?
9. How much do you love your mother?
10. To which extent you ignore your interests and claims in the favor of other family members?
11. To which extent do you ignore traveling your in the favor of other family members?
12. How much is your mother patient?
13. How much is your father patient?
14. How much will you be worried if your father faces a problem?

15. How much will you be worried if your mother faces a problem?

B. Domestic Violence (Dependent Variables)

One of the most common methods of measuring child exposure, as stated earlier, is to adapt the adult Conflict Tactics Scales [27],[28] for use with children. Kolbo [29] utilized the same seven-point scale as the original CTS, with responses ranging from "Never" to "Over 20 Times"

VAC will be category to 3 levels: 1- emotional abuse 2- physical abuse 3- neglect.

For measuring VAC used been CTS scale: Each independent variables by codes : 0=never, 1 = once, 2 = twice, 3 = 3-5 times, 4 = 6-10 times, 5 = 11-20 times, 6 =over 20 times. e.g. questions raised to this way:" How many times has it happened that your father has prevented you from speaking during the last year?"

Never One time Two times 3-5 times 6-10 times 11-20 times Over 20 times

operational dependent variables (VAC) are available at Table II.

Questioner of violence against the children:

1. How many times has it happened that your father has prevented you of speaking during the last year?
2. How many times has it happened that your father has insulted you during last year?
3. How many times has it happened that your father has broken self esteem your during last year?
4. How many times has it happened that your father has prevented you of playing during last year?
5. How many times has it happened that your father threat ed you during last year?
6. How many times has it happened that your father shouted you during last year?
7. How many times has it happened that your father forced you do sth during last year?
8. How many times has it happened that your father has been injustice during last year?
9. How many times has it happened that your father neglected your sickness during last year?
10. How many times has it happened that your father neglected your being late you during last year?
11. How many times has it happened that your father has prevented you of going to school during last year?
12. How many times has it happened that your father forced you to leave home during last year?
13. How many times has it happened that your father pushed you during last year?
14. How many times has it happened that your father beat you during last year?
15. How many times has it happened that your father punished with belt during last year?
16. How many times has it happened that your father brand you during last year?

III. RESULT

Result of descriptive order in family:

Table I show descriptive statistic of order in family, in this table we see percent of variables: collective thinking, empathy, company, communal circumstance. The frequency of distribution of order in family shown in Table I. mean of variables among (0-6) have been scaled: code (0) never, code (1) very little, code (2) little, code (3) moderate, code (4) much, code (5) very much, code (6) ever. **collective thinking:** highest mean for collective thinking is variable of consult on children nurture, the other variables are: consult on buying house wares (mean=5.15), consult on families meeting (mean =4.93), consult (mean=4.90). **empathy:** highest mean for empathy is variable children love to mother (mean=5.03), the other variables are: children love to father (mean=4.90), mother love to children (mean = 4.76) love parent to children (mean=4.66), parent love to each other (mean=4.51). **Company:** Highest mean for company is variable ignore traveling children in the favor of other family members (mean=3.65) and after is ignore children interests and claims in the favor of other family members (mean=3.59). **Communal circumstance:** Highest mean for communal circumstance is variable of children worry if mother faces a problem (mean = 4.64), the other variables are: children worry if father faces a problem (mean=4.56), mother patient (mean =4.49) father patient (mean=4.31). Concerning compute of variables of order in family, mean order in family is 4.40 among 0-6, this illustrate order in family is high (more than much), the most share of order in family is empathy (mean 4.79) in family and the others are : communal circumstance (mean 4.5), collective thinking (mean 4.08) and company (mean 3.62).

TABLE I
DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCIES ORDER IN FAMILY

mean	ever	Very much	much	moderate	little	Very little	never	variable	index
3/90	18%	15.5%	24%	30.5%	6%	5.5%	.5%	consult	Collective thinking
4.35	19.55	25.5%	34%	14.2%	3%	2.5%	.5%	Consult on children nurture	
3.93%	16.9%	28.5%	27.2%	22.1%	10.8%	3.6%	1%	Consult on families meeting	
4.15%	17.3%	32.5%	17.3%	21.3%	6.1%	4.5%	1%	Consult on buying house wares	
4.51	25.9	31.5%	21.8%	13.2%	5.6%	1%	1%	Parent love to each other	empathy
4.66	36.9%	37.9%	12.8%	6.7%	3.1%	1.5%	1%	father love to children	
4.87	34%	35.5%	18%	10%	2%		.5%	mother love to children	
4.90	36.9%	37.9%	12.8%	6.7%	3.1%	1.5%	1%	Children love to father	
5.03	40.8%	35.7%	14.8%	4.6%	2.6%	1.5%		Children love to mother	company
3.59	10.5%	26.2%	17.3%	22%	11.5%	7.9%	4.7%	children ignore your interest in the favor of other members	
3.65	10.9%	22.9%	19.8%	16.1%	12%	10.9%	6.8%	children ignore your travel in the favor of other members	
4.40	27.4%	32%	17.3%	9.6%	7.1%	4.1%	2.5%	Mother patient	communal circumstance
4.31	22.4%	34.7%	18.9%	11.2%	4.6%	5.1%	3.1%	Father patient	
4.56	24.1%	44.2%	14.1%	9.5%	1.5%	2.5%	4%	Children worry if father faces a problem	
4.64	26.3%	44.4%	14.6%	6.1%	2.5%	3%	3%	Children worry if mother faces a problem	

IV. RESULT DESCRIPTIVE OF VAC

Table II show the results of descriptive of VAC (dependence variable) mean and frequencies of variables among (0-7) have been scaled :code (0) never, code (1) one time, code (2) two times, code (3) 3-5 times , code (4) 6-10 times, code (5) 11-20 times, code (6) more 20 times.

Emotional abuse: highest mean (among never- over 20 time) for Emotional abuse of father is variable of preventing from speak (mean=1.79), that ,62% children have experienced the violence at more than once during the last year, and other variables are: shouting (mean=1.77) that 65.8% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year , force to doing Sth (mean=1.62) that 54.8% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year , Depriving of play (mean=1.57) that 55.5% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, insulting (mean=1.47) that 48% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year that highest frequency is two times that this frequency is 12%, Breaking of self esteem (mean=1.43) 49% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year , treating (mean =1.31) that 46.5% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year , injustice (mean=1.1) that 37.9% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year.

Neglect : highest mean for neglect is variable of neglect to sickness (mean =.85) that 28.5% children have experienced the violence at least once during the more than, and the others variables are: Neglect to being late (mean = .84) that 36.7% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, forcing to leave home (mean = .53) that 20.2% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, preventing from going to school (mean = .32) that 15.6% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year.

Physical abuse: highest mean for Physical abuse is variable of beating (mean =1.23) that 51.5% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, and after as follows: pushing (mean =.78) that 36.7% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, punishing with belt (mean =.51) that 18.8% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, branding that 8% children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year. Concerning compute of variables violence against the children, mean VAC in family among never (0) – over 20 times (6) is 1.06. Illustrate children have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, the most share of violence in family is emotional abuse (mean 1.6) and others : physical abuse(mean .67),neglect (mean .63) .

TABLE II
 DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCIES OF VAC

means	Over 20 times	11-20 times	6-10 times	3-5 times	Two times	One time	never	variables	index
1.79	7.5%	3%	8%	15.1%	13.6%	14.6%	38.2%	Preventing from speaking	Father's emotional abuse
1.47	5%	3%	9%	6.5%	12%	11.5%	52.5%	insulting	
1.43	9.5%	2%	3%	9.5%	11%	14%	51%	Breaking of self esteem	
1.57	5.5%	2.5%	8%	14.5%	11%	14%	44.5%	Depriving of play	
1.31	5.5%	1.5%	9.5%	5%	13%	12%	53.5%	treating	
1.77	9%	3%	6%	10.1%	16.6%	21.1%	34.2%	shouting	
1.62	8%	4%	7.5%	9.5%	10.11%	15.6%	45.2%	Force to doing sth	
1.1	5.6%	2.5%	2.5%	9.1%	9.1%	9.1%	62.1%	injustice	neglect
.85	4.5%	1.5%	3.5%	5%	7.5%	6.5%	71.5%	neglect to sickness	
.84	3.5%	1.5%	3.5%	4%	9%	12.1%	66.3%	Neglect to being late	
.32	0	0	3%	1.5%	5%	6%	84.4%	Preventing from going to school	
.53	1%	.5%	2%	5.1%	4.5%	6.6%	79.8%	Force to leaving home	
.78	1.5%	1.5%	2%	5.5%	11.6%	14.6%	63.3%	pushing	
1.23	5.6%	.5%	4%	7.1%	15.7%	18.7%	48.5%	beating	
.51	1.5%	3%	0	5.1%	3%	6.1%	81.2%	Punishing with belt	
.19	.5%	0	1%	1.5%	2.5%	2.5%	92%	branding	

Table III show the results variables of VAM(father to mother) mean of variables and distribution of frequencies, among 0-7 have been scaled :code (0) never, code (1) one time, code (2)two times , code (3) 3-5 times , code (4) 6-10 times, code (5) 11-20 times, code (6) over 20 times.

Highest mean for VAM is physical abuse (mean =1) that 29.6% that mothers have experienced the violence more than

once during the last year, and after it verbal abuse (mean =.74) that 32.2% mothers have experienced the violence more than once during the last year, and the end leaving home that 16.5% mothers have experienced the violence more than once during the last year (mean =.35).

TABLE III
 DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCIES VAM

means	over 20 times	11-20 times	6-10 times	3-5 times	Two times	One time	never	variable
.74	3.5%	1%	2.5%	3.5%	7%	13.6%	68.8%	Verbal abuse
1	2.5%	.5%	2.5%	5.5%	7%	10.6%	71.4%	Physical abuse
.35	.5%	.5%	1%	2.5%	5.5%	5.5%	84.5%	Leaving home

V. STATISTIC TESTS

By Pearson test correlation between independent variables and VAC show this result (Table IV): Concerning Table IV, effect of collective thinking on VAC is significance (intensity = -.319, sig = 000), that illustrate the increase of collective thinking in family, decrease VAC, effect of empathy on VAC is significance (intensity = -.441, sig = 000), that illustrate the increase of empathy in family ,decrease VAC, effect of

communal circumstance on VAC is significance (intensity = -.208, sig = 000), that illustrate the increase of communal circumstance in family, decrease VAC. Which means the variables of collective thinking, empathy and communal circumstance will decrease the amount VAC, which in turn verifies the interaction effects families' violence against the children.

TABLE IV
 PEARSON TEST CORRELATION AMONG VAC N AND ORDER IN FAMILY

	collective thinking	empathy	communal Co-circumstance
VAC	-.319**	-.441**	-.208**

**p < .01

Concerning to Table V effect of collective thinking on violence of VAM is significance (intensity = -.268, sig = 000), that illustrate t the increase of thinking collective in family decrease VAM, effect of empathy on VAM is significance (intensity = -.296, sig = 000), that illustrate increase of

empathy in family decrease VAM, effect of communal circumstance on VAM is significance (intensity = -.178, sig = 000), that illustrate increase of communal circumstance in family decrease VAM.

TABLE V
 PEARSON TEST CORRELATION AMONG INDEPENDENT VARIABLES AND VAM

	collective thinking	empathy	communal circumstance
VAM	-.268**	-.296**	-.178**

By test of independent sample T-test, different between variable of sex and violence against the children is significant (sig = 000), mean violence for female is 1.56(among 0-6) and

for male mean of violence is 2.36 (among 0- 6), which shows that the female feel less from violence their father compared with the males (Table VI).

TABLE VI
 INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T – TEST BETWEEN SEX AND VAC

	mean		Significance (2 tailed) 000
VAC	male	female	
	2.36	1.52	

F=25.521
 Df=182.339

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates the effects of order in family VAC in a survey method. For defining children VAC we have used theories which emphasis on factors of relations and interaction among family members. Order in family with regard to the following variables has been operational as a whole. The rate of order family is 4.40 among 0-6.with CTS scale VAC has been operational and its rate is 1.06 among 0-7, that children have experienced more than once during the last year. Variables collective thinking empathy, communal circumstance are significant, this shows its important in realizing the effective factors on violence in family, in other words relationships among family effect on violence in family, then this research prove theories factors relating to intra-family relationships.

Among the peripheral variables only the sex variable is significant, which shows that the female feel less violence from their father compared with the males. The other peripheral variables e.g income, education and profession related to family violence are not significant. All these show that VAC is more related to relational factors in inter of family. What should be mentioned here is that the effects of variables should be regard on delinquency factor.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Fantuzzo, J., Boruch, R., Beriama, A., Atkins, M., & Marcus, S. (1997). *Domestic violence and children: Prevalence and risk in five major U.S. cities*. Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry.
- [2] Christian, C. W., Scribano, P., Seidl, T., & Pinto-Martin, J. (1997). *Pediatric injury resulting from family violence*. Pediatrics, 99. Retrieved from <http://www.pediatrics.org/cgi/content/full/99/2/e8>
- [3] Kaufman, J., & Henrich, C. (2000). *Exposure to violence and early childhood trauma*. In C. H. Zeanah (Ed.), Handbook of infant mental health (2nd ed.). New York: The Guilford Press.
- [4] DiLauro, M. D. (2004). *Psychosocial factors associated with types of child maltreatment*. Child Welfare.
- [5] Gail Hornor, (2005) "Domestic Violence and Children" Journal of Pediatric Health Care.
- [6] Maughan, A., & Cicchetti, D. (2002). *Impact of child maltreatment and inter adult violence on children's emotion regulation abilities and socio-emotional adjustment*. Child Development, 73, 1525-1542.
- [7] Appel, A. E., & Holden, G. W. (1998). *The co-occurrence of spouse and physical child abuse: A review and appraisal*. Journal of Family Psychology.

- [8] Grych, J. H., Jouriles, E. N., Swank, P. R., McDonald, R., & Norwood, W. D. (2000). *Patterns of adjustment among children of battered women*. Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology.
- [9] Wolfe DA.(2006), *Preventing violence in relationships: psychological science addressing complex social issues*.
- [10] Jeffrey L. Edleson, Amanda L. Ellerton, Ellen A. Seagren, Staci L. Kirchberg, Sarah. Schmidt, Amirithini T. Ambrose (2007), "Assessing child exposure to adult domestic violence", Children and Youth Services Review.
- [11] Australian Bureau of Statistics. (1996). *Women's Safety Survey*. Commonwealth of Australia.
- [12] Smith, Jennifer. (1994). *The Effects of Domestic Violence on Young Children: A Brisbane study*. Shattering the Silence.
- [13] Straus, M. A. (1992). *Children as witnesses to marital violence: a risk factor for lifelong problems among a nationally*.
- [14] Carlson, B. E. (2000). *Children exposed to intimate partner violence: Research findings and implications for intervention* Trauma, Violence, and Abuse.
- [15] Thompson, M. P., Saltzman, L. E., & Johnson, H. (2003). *A comparison of risk factors for intimate partner violence-related injury across two national surveys on violence against women*. Violence Against Women.
- [16] Kitzmann, K. M., Gaylord, N. K., Holt, A. R., & Kenny, E. D. (2003). *Child witnesses to domestic violence: A metaanalytic review*. Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology.
- [17] Wolfe, D. A., Crooks, C. V., Lee, V., McIntyre-Smith, A., & Jaffe, P. G. (2003). *The effects of children's exposure to domestic violence: A meta-analysis and critique*. Clinical Child and Family Psychology Review.
- [18] V. Mehra,(2004) *Culturally competent responses for identifying and responding to domestic violence in dental care settings*, California Dent.
- [19] B. J. Dattel, R. Chez,(1996) *Women domestic violence and the obstetrician/gynecologist*, primary Care Update.
- [20] Genevieve Lessard, Chantal Lavergne, Claire Chamberland, (2005)Dominique Damant Daniel Turcotte *Conditions for resolving controversies between social actors in domestic violence and youth protection services: Toward innovative collaborative practices* Canada, 19 August.
- [21] Irwin J. & Wilkinson M. (1996). *Women, children and domestic violence*. Women against Violence.
- [22] Leavitt,Jerome E. (1993),*child abuse and neglect: Research and Innovation*, Martinus Nijhof Publishers.
- [23] Graham-Bermann, S. A. (2001). *Designing intervention evaluations for children exposed to domestic violence: Applications of research and theory*.
- [24] Hampton, Robert & gullota, Thomas P. (1993), *family violence* ,sage
- [25] Reder,peter & Duncan ,Silvia,lost (1999), Innocents: *Follow up Study of Fatal Child Abuse*,Londen,Routledge.
- [26] Chalabi , massuod and rasolzadehaghdam , samad (2002) *the effect of order and conflict in the family upon violence against children*, Iranian journal of sociology vol.4,no.2,summer.
- [27] Straus, M. A. (1979). *Measuring intrafamily conflict and violence: The conflict tactics (CT) scales*. Journal of Marriage and the Family.
- [28] Straus, M. A., Hamby, S. L., Boney-McCoy, S., & Sugarman, D. B. (1996). *The revised conflict tactics scales (CTS2): Development and preliminary psychometric data*. Journal of Family Issues.
- [29] Kolbo, J. R. (1996). *Risk and resilience among children exposed to family violence*. Violence and Victims.